

Studies on the Interaction of Metal Ions with Casein

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The binding of copper, zinc, magnesium, manganese and strontium with casein has been studied employing pH-metric method. The binding was calculated per 100 gms. of protein. The studies reveal that these metal ions combine with the protein mainly through the carboxyl groups. Copper and zinc bind with the imidazole groups also while manganese and strontium show little tendency to do so. Magnesium shows no tendency to combine with the imidazole groups. Polarographic reduction of the copper casein complex gives two waves. The $E_{1/2}$ of the first wave corresponds to the $E_{1/2}$ of the violet copper complex of the biuret base.

The interaction of heavy metal ions with casein has not been extensively investigated, due to the complex nature of the latter and the uncertainty about its molecular weight. Mallender¹ demonstrated that the casein contains three components, α , β and γ -caseins. Hipp and Co-workers² separated these components and also attempted to correlate the properties of these components with those of whole casein. These investigations, however, could not give a correct answer to the problem regarding their molecular weight. It was only recently when Wake and Baldwin³ showed that the casein is a mixture of at least twenty components. Waugh^{4,5} separated the α fraction into α_1 caseins and precisely determined their molecular weight. With this information at hand it is now possible to carry out quantitative studies on the binding of heavy metals with this protein. The electrometric studies with whole casein were undertaken making use of the data available on the dissociable groups from hydrogen ion equilibria studies⁵.

In the present communication the results of the pH metric studies on the interaction of copper, zinc magnesium, manganese and strontium with casein along with the data on the polarography of copper-casein mixtures are described. These investigations will be followed by those on metal α -casein interaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Casein used for these studies was prepared by the following method⁶:

The pure casein (E. Merck) was soaked in water and then dissolved in dilute ammonia, the pH of the solution was kept below 7.0. The casein was precipitated by adding calculated amount of dilute acetic acid. The casein was washed several times with water and then finally centrifuged. The washed casein, after centrifugation was finally stored under water with toluene in a refrigerator.

1. Mallender, *Biochem. Z.*, 1939, 240, 300.
2. Hipp, Groves and McMaskin *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 4822.
3. Wake and Baldwin, *Biochem. et Biophys. Acta*, 1961, 47, 226.
4. Waugh et al., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 4938.
5. Waugh et al., *ibid.*, 1962, 84, 4938.

The casein so obtained was dissolved in minimum amount of 0.1M KOH (the pH was kept below 7.0). The solution was centrifuged and its concentration was checked by drying an aliquot (10 ml.) in a weighed crucible at 105° for about four hours. The correct concentration was determined by applying correction for potassium (added in the form of KOH).

The procedure was the same as communicated earlier^{3,4}. The pH measurements were made with the help of Cambridge Bench pH-meter reading up to 0.02 pH units and the glass electrodes. A special blue cap 'alki' glass electrode was used for the more alkaline solutions. Potassium acid phthalate and borax were used for the standardisation of the pH meter for the acid and the alkaline ranges of pH. The binding was calculated as described in an earlier communication. In the present case the binding has been calculated per 10³ gms. of protein.

Polarographic measurements* were carried out with the help of Fisher Electrode in conjunction with the Multiflex galvanometer in the external circuit. H-type cell was used. It was kept immersed in a thermostat maintained at temperature 30±0.1°. Purified nitrogen was used for deaeration. Potassium hydroxide used to study the complex in the higher pH range, was employed as the supporting electrolyte. The drop time was kept as 3.3 seconds in the open circuit, the sensitivity of the galvanometer was 1:10.

DISCUSSION

pH-metry: In view of the uncertainty of molecular weight of whole casein it is difficult to give correct quantitative data on the binding of metal ions by this protein. In the present studies it has, however, been calculated per 10³ gm. of protein. The binding of hydrogen ions with casein has also been calculated per 10³ gms. of casein by some earlier workers.

The titration curves obtained in presence and absence of protein are quite different, giving thereby a clear indication of the binding of the metal ions with the different groups of the casein. At pH 5.50, where the binding is with the carboxyl groups (log K for carboxyl groups is about 5.1), the number of protons liberated are 25, 12, 6, 7, 4 for copper, zinc, magnesium, manganese and strontium respectively.

As discussed in our earlier communication^{6,7,8} the numbers of protons liberated in presence of metal ions give indirectly the number of metal ions bound to the protein molecule because one-to-one binding is usually favoured. In the present case the number of protons liberated may be taken as a measure of the number of metal ions bound per 10³ gms. of casein. From the data summarised in Table I, it is evident that copper has got the maximum capacity of binding to the carboxyl groups of casein followed by zinc, magnesium, manganese and strontium. The affinity of magnesium and manganese seems to be equal, as they both liberate equal number of protons. The order of their binding tendency with carboxyl groups is copper > zinc > magnesium > manganese > strontium.

*Experimental data taken from Ph.D. thesis of A.A. Khan, 1960 (Aligarh Muslim University).

6. Malik and Muzaffaruddin, *Experientia*, 1965, 21, 233.

7. Malik and Muzaffaruddin, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1965, 18, 1897.

8. Malik and Muzaffaruddin, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1963, 8, 214.

In the slightly alkaline pH range (pH 7-8) the imidazole groups are available for the binding. The maximum number of groups available for binding is 20. At this pH all the metals excepting magnesium liberated limited number of protons, showing their binding with the imidazole groups. The numbers of metal ions bound to the imidazole groups are 3, 3, 1 and 2 in case of copper, zinc, manganese and strontium respectively. These data also support the fact that copper and zinc have strong affinities for the binding with the imidazole groups.

Polarography: Although casein forms violet complex in the higher pH range, the composition of the complex obtained under this condition could not be established due to its non-reducibility in excess of the protein. Polarographic reduction, however, was possible after the saturation of protein solution with copper sulphate. Two wave polarograms with $E_{1/2}$ value: 0.78V and 1.26V. for the first and the second waves respectively are

obtained. The $E_{1/2}$ of the first wave corresponded to the $E_{1/2}$ of the violet copper complex of the biuret base. From this it may be concluded that casein gives a biuret reaction with copper ions.

TABLE I

Binding data calculated per 10⁵ gms. of casein.

pH	H ⁺ dissociated in presence of metal ions.	H ⁺ dissociated in absence of metal ions.	V _M
Cu²⁺ —casein system			
5.50	103	138	25
6.35	190	165	25
7.50	218	190	28
8.00	226	196	30
Zn²⁺ —casein system			
5.50	150	138	12
6.35	178	165	13
7.50	206	190	15
8.00	212	196	16
Mg²⁺ —casein system			
5.50	145	138	7
6.35	171	165	6
7.50	196	190	6
8.00	203	196	7
Mn²⁺ —casein system			
5.50	145	138	7
6.35	172	165	7
7.50	198	190	8
8.00	204	196	8
Sr²⁺ —casein system			
5.50	142	138	4
6.35	170	165	4
7.50	196	190	6
8.00	205	196	7